

Original Research Article

The Attitude of Lecturers towards the Utilization of Library Resources and Services in Adamawa State Polytechnic Yola, Nigeria

Sani Yusuf* and Aishatu Ahmed Rufai

Abstract

Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
saniyusuf286@gmail.com

This survey is carried out to ascertain the attitude of the lecturers towards the utilization of library resources and services in Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola. Four (4) objectives and Four (40) research questions guided the study. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire administered on one hundred and twenty (120) lecturers in Adamawa State Polytechnic drawn from various colleges and departments in the main campus. One hundred (100) out of one hundred and twenty (120) questionnaires were returned for the analyses. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics comprising frequency distribution and percentages. The response rate was one hundred (100) representing 83.3% the results indicate amongst others that majority of the lecturers do not utilize the library effectively but occasionally when need arises. The study further revealed that majority of the lecturers are not satisfied with the resources and services rendered in the library. The study revealed that lack of conducive environment, internet services, up-to-date materials, relevant resources etc, are the factors militating against utilization of resources and services by the lecturers in Adamawa State Polytechnic. Therefore, it was recommended among others that there should be provision of internet services in the library to meet the needs and interest of the lecturers in Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola.

Keywords: Adamawa State Polytechnic, Attitude, Lecturers, Library resources, Library services

INTRODUCTION

Information is the most powerful tool in learning endeavors. Libraries are collections of information in organized ways to make it accessible to the target audience. The main challenge, however, is the underutilization of library resources by lecturers and student in learning institutions, as observed by Jamila Aliokluk (2020).

According to Saunders (2015), academic libraries are valuable facilities in any learning institution because they provide an environment for students to advance their

knowledge. Libraries are also valuable to teaching staff because they provide an enabling research environment.

Academic libraries considered the “heart” of a learning institution. Libraries must be structured to support the learning needs. Nonetheless, an interesting observation is that there is an underutilization of the library facilities in most institutions, which is counterproductive to the goals and objectives of the library unit with regard to information. Chen (2015); Ibrahim and Sakiyo (2015). Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain as to

why the lecturers of Adamawa state polytechnic Yola, are not using the library resources and services that have been made available for their use.

Statement of the problem

According to Delivery and Bates (2015), the library is an important learning resource in any academic institution. Recent trends and advancements in technology have led to the modernization of library services, including the development of vast online databases with a wealth of information to guide learning and research.

However, despite these developments, the utilization of library services is not optimal in most learning institution, which limits the realization of educational benefits that arise from library use. It has come to our knowledge and observation that the lecturers of this great institution, Adamawa state polytechnic Yola, do not visit the library not to talk of utilizing the resources or refer students to use the resources made available to them. P2

It is out of this concern that the decision to go into this research came into being. Jamila Aloklu (2020) observed.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To determine the current rate of utilization of library services by lecturers of Adamawa State Polytechnic Yola.
2. To determine the lecturers satisfaction with the library services in the Polytechnic.
3. To identify barriers against the utilization of resources and services by lecturers in Adamawa State Polytechnic.
4. To identify potential solutions to improve the utilization of library services in Adamawa State Polytechnic.

Research questions

The following research questions correlate with the specific objectives of the study

1. What is the current rate of library services utilization by lecturers of Adamawa State Polytechnic?
2. Are lecturers satisfied with the current library services in Adamawa state polytechnic?
3. What are the barriers against the use of library facilities by lecturers of Adamawa State Polytechnic?
4. What can be done to eliminate these barriers?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

1. The study will help to know why the lecturers don't come to the library to use the resource made available.

2. The result of this study will make the management of this library to know what step they will take to encourage the use of the resources available in the library especially by the lecturers P3

3. The study will also serves as a source of literature to other researchers who may take on further research in this field. It will also help the management in policy making and formulation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A study on the attitude of student towards the library facilities, states the importance of libraries to education generally lies in the fact they provide necessary information to lecturers, student and researchers and community service. Jamila Alokiuk (2020). The significance of academic libraries lies in the fact that provides the vital underpinning for national development.

Earlier studies by Kannappanavar and Manjunatha (2010), and Majid et al. (2000) had observed that professional in some Saudi Universities visited their libraries often.

Popoola and Zaid (2008) undertook a study titled faculty awareness and use of library information products and services in Nigerian Universities. Dickenson (2006) in an academic library impact study (ALIS), of academic library usage and outcomes, involving nine colleges and universities, undertake that faculty members use libraries, because of the resources they provide. Faculty members use libraries to fulfill a need, that fulfillment which would enable them perform their duties or achieve various objectives and goals. The survey also showed that, the majority of faculty members indicated that, they frequently or sometimes placed print materials on the traditional reserved services at their institution's library for their students, and also recommended print resources. Again, in the ALIS study, some faculty members said that they have frequently, or sometimes used electronic reserve services through their college or university library. The survey also revealed that, the majority of them search library catalogues other than their library's websites.

In a survey conducted by Sharma (2009), to analyze the dependency of teachers and research scholars on e-resources on their academic efficiency, and problems faced by them whilst using the e-resources the perceived impact of the e-resources on their academic efficiency, and problems faced by them whilst using the e-resources to include journals, P4

data archives, manuscripts, maps, books, magazines, theses, newspapers, e-mails, research report, and bibliographic data bases.

The results showed that the use of e-resources was very common among teachers, and research scholars in India and research scholars were dependent on e-resources to get the designed and relevant information.

Table 1. Response rate

Questionnaires	Frequencies	Percentage
Total copies administered	120	100%
Total copies returned	100	83.3%
Total copies not returned	20	16.7%

Table 2. Gender

Gender	No of respondent	Frequencies	Percentage
Male	100	80	80%
Female	100	20	20%

Table 3. Lecturers' visit to the library

S/n	Statement	No of respondents	Frequencies	Percentage
1	Yes	100	45	45%
2	No	100	55	55%

Table 4. Utilization of library resources and services by lecturers in a Month

S/n	Statement	No of respondents	Frequencies	Percentage
1	I do not use the library	100	55	55%
2	Once a Month	100	30	30%
3	Twice a Month	100	10	10%
4	Once a week	100	5	5%
5	Twice a week	100	—	—

Morse and Clint worth (2000) opined that, Electronic resources are now used more than print resources. House right and Schonfeld (2010), however, observed that since 2000, faculty members have steadily been shifting towards reliance on network-level electronic resources, and a corresponding decline in interest in using locally provided tools for discovery of books, journals, and other materials. The study concluded that, while print journals may continue to play a limited role for faculty with specific needs that are otherwise poorly met, digital versions are clearly the medium of choice for most faculty members.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study was the survey method and the target population was all the lecturers in the main campus of Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola. Questionnaires were used as instrument of Data collection, to obtained necessary information for this study. Lecturers were required to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement on negative statement of Items 1-5, using the adopted liker scale of rank ordering. Out of one hundred and twenty (120) copies of the questionnaire distributed, one hundred (100) copies

representing % were duly completed and returned. The Data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency and percentage. P5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the table 1 above, it indicate that 120 questionnaires were distributed while 100 representing 83.3% were returned and used for the analyses. From the table 2 above, it indicate that 80% of the respondents were male lecturers while 20% of them were female lecturers.

The table 3 above revealed that 45 (45%) of the respondents answered Yes meaning the visit the library while 55 (55%) of them responded No, which shows that majority of the lecturers in Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola, do not visit the library. P6

Chiwar, M. A. (2011), opined that the polytechnic libraries are supposed to make available resources that are relevant and current for sustaining teaching and research activities of the academic community.

The table 4 above revealed that an average of 55(55%) of the respondents said they do not use the library resources and services at all, while 30 (30%) of

Table 5. Purpose of visit to the library by lecturers

S/n	Statement	No of respondents	Frequencies	Percentage
1	meeting friends	100	25	25%
2	use of the internet	100	20	20%
3	read newspapers	100	10	10%
4	borrow library books	100	15	15%
5	use library materials within building	100	35	35%
6	read personal study notes	100	15	15%
7	use printing and photocopy	100	15	15%
8	other reasons	100	35	35%

Table 6. Perception of the library by the lecturers

Statement	No of Respondent	(SA)	(A)	(N)	(D)	(SD)
		Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%
The library provide study space and conducive environment	100	15/15%	25/25%	___	5/5%	10/10%
The library provide access to useful study materials	100	10/10%	25/25	40/40%	10/10%	15/15%
The library provide adequate Resources to help me stay updated With my area of research	100	10/105	15/15%	35/35%	20/20%	20/20%
The library helps me to cultivate a habit of self study	100	10/10%	40/40%	35/35%	10/10%	5/5%

Key: SA= strongly agreed, A=agreed, N= neutral, D= disagreed, SD= strongly disagreed

Table 7. I perceived the library as

Statement	No of respondent	(SA)	(A)	(N)	(D)	(SD)
		Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%
Having contributed to the Improvement of my academic performance	100	10/10%	20/20%	30/30%	30/30%	10/10%
A place for study	100	15/15%	30/30%	30/30%	10/10%	15/15%
A place of socialization	100	20/20%	15/15%	45/45%	10/10%	10/10%
A place to verify information Taught in class by teachers	100	15/15%	30/30%	50/50%	5/5%	___/___
A place to widen my scope Of knowledge	100	20/20%	25/25%	40/40%	10/10	5/5%
A very important facility for Any learning institution	100	10/10%	10/10%	20/20%	15/15%	45/45%
A no-go-area	100	10/10%	10/10%	45/45%	25/25%	10/10%

Key: SA= strongly agreed, A=agreed, N= neutral, D= disagreed, SD= strongly Disagreed

them said they visit the library once a month, which indicate that utilization of library resources and services by the lecturers is low. This finding is contrary Olanlukun (1983), where he discovered that the majority of the faculty members had the tendency to utilize the library once a week.

From the table 5 above, revealed that 25 (25%) of the respondents do visit the library to meet their friends, while 35 (35%) of them use the library materials within the library building.

From the table 6 above, the perception of lecturers

towards the library, analyses revealed that 40% of the respondent expresses their disagreement with the provision of adequate resources and services to help them stay updated in their area of research, while 40% of the respondent remains neutral with regard to that, which shows the majority of the respondent have low confident with the library with regard to the provision of adequate resources and services. P8

The table 7 above revealed that 60 (60%) of the respondent disagreed with the library as a place to widen their scope of knowledge, while 50 (50%) of the

Table 8. Lecturer's satisfaction with the library resources and services

Statement	No of respondent	(SA)	(A)	(N)	(D)	(SD)
		Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%	Freq/%
The collection of information is current and pertinent to my study area	100	10/10%	25/25%	40/40%	20/20%	5/5%
The publicity on the important Of the importance of the library Resources is okay	100	5/5%	20/20%	45/45%	20/20%	20/20%
There is bad physical facilities	100	/	20/20%	40/40%	20/20%	20/20%
There is wrong opening hours Of the library	100	5/5%	15/15%	35/35%	15/15%	30/30%
The attitude of the library staffs is bad	100	10/10%	10/10%	45/45%	25/25%	10/10%

Key: SA= strongly agreed, A=agreed, N= neutral, D= disagreed, SD= strongly disagreed

respondents remains neutral with regard to the library as a place to verify information taught in the lass by teachers.

From the table 8 above, the results shows that 35 (35%) of the respondents expresses their dissatisfaction with the library resources and services, which 40-45 (40-45%) of the respondents remains Neutral. P10

With these findings, it indicate that majority of the respondents are not satisfied with the library resources and services rendered in Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the research findings, it can be concluded that lecturers of Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola, are willing to utilize the library resources and services provided the library can provide adequate resources and services that are current and relevant in all the fields of the academic community. Under utilization is inevitable when the reverse is the case as shown in the results. It is as a result of these problems that the study recommended that the library management should always liaise with the lecturers in selecting and acquiring the relevant and current library resources and services. The study also recommended that there should be provision of internet services in the library to meet the technological advancement challenges and pave way for the lecturers to have access to e-books, and other electronic materials. In addition, the Polytechnic authority should

provide adequate funds to the library and all the necessary facilities that will warrant conducive atmosphere to encourage the utilization of library resources and services.

REFERENCES

- Amkpa SA (2005). Information services and lecturers utilization of libraries in Federal Universities of technology in Nigeria. PhD Dissertation submitted to Department of Educational Technology and Library Science University of Uyo, Uyo.
- Artal R, Rubinfeld S (2017). ' Ethical Issues in Research', Best Practice and Research Clinical Obstetrics & Gynaecology, vol. 43, pp. 107-114.
- Chiwar MA (2015). Academic Staff Awareness and Use of Library Resources and Services in Nigeria. Journal of research in Education and society, International perspectives. Vol. 6 no. 3 pp.18-25 P11
- Creswell JW (2014). Research design: quantitative, qualitative and Mixed methods approach, 4th Ed, Sage Publication Inc, Los Angeles. CA.
- Edoka BE (2000). Introduction to Library Science. Onitsha: Palma publishing and Links Company Ltd.
- Ibrahim,F.L. & Sakiyo, J (2015), Aesthetics and utilization of University libraries in north east zone of Nigeria, information impact: J. Info. Knowledge Manag. Vol.6. no. 3. Pp.1-20
- Jamila, A. PhD. (2000), Attitude of Students towards the Use of Library Facilities: A Case Study. International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education. Volume 7, Issue 1, PP 24-36
- Shapma G (2017). 'Pros and Cons of different sampling techniques', Int. J. Appl. Res. vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 749-752. P12